

Evaluation of skin-core effects in thick CFRTP laminates by embedded optical fiber sensors and mechanical tests

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermo-plastic (CFRTP) has several advantages such as high-cycle manufacturing and good mechanical property. Hence CFRTP is recently expected to be applied to primary structures of aircraft and automobile. When we manufacture a thick CFRTP product, it is difficult to suppress temperature distribution in the through-thickness direction under practical high-cycle processing condition. Since the thermoplastic does not have a curing reaction, the start time of solidification differs between the surface and central part of the laminate. This difference leads to the residual stress/strain and material property distribution. This phenomenon is called “skin-core effects”. However, skin-core effects have not been investigated in detail. Therefore, this study evaluates the residual stress/strain and mechanical property distribution due to the skin-core effects in thick CFRTP laminates. We evaluated residual strain distribution in CF/PPS thick UD laminates by embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. They were placed near the surface and central of the laminate. In the test, specimens were cooled by three methods which resulted in different temperature and cooling speed distributions. Residual strain depending on the cooling method was successfully characterized. It could be estimated that in the rapidly cooled specimen tensile (compressive) stress existed in the central (surface) part after molding. Furthermore, the residual strain changed after the subsequent annealing in case that the crystallinity did not reach the maximal level. Finally, the effects of residual stress distribution on the mechanical property were evaluated by tensile tests of cross-ply thick laminates. The density of the transverse cracks in the 90-degree layers was non-uniform in the specimen affected by the skin-core effects. It was confirmed that premature cracks occurred due to the residual tensile stress at the central part.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermo-plastic (CFRTP) has many advantages such as short-time manufacturing, reformability and high toughness [1]. Different types of thermoplastics are used as matrices of CFRTPs; PEEK, PPS, and PEI resins come up for the matrix of high-performance CFRTP that is used in aircraft structures because of their great material characteristics such as impact, heat, and chemical resistances. In recent years, the size and thickness of products are increasing as CFRTP is applied to the primary structures. In thick CFRTP structures, however, non-uniform temperature and cooling speed distribution are generated during the cooling process especially in the through-thickness direction. As a result, the start time of solidification/crystallization differs between the surface and central part of the laminates. Moreover, temperature distribution changes the material property and residual stress/strain distribution. This phenomenon is called “skin-core effects” [2-3].

Some studies reported on skin-core effects. Reference [4-5] evaluated the material property distribution due to skin-core effects. However, these studies have issues with cooling methods which relate directly to skin-core effects. For example, the temperature distribution is too small to generate

these effects in Ref. [4] and single-side cooling was used in Ref. [5], which is impractical. Moreover, they could not evaluate how internal states changed in real time. A new in-situ method to monitor internal states of CFRTP laminates is necessary to evaluate skin-core effects under high temperature and pressure conditions.

Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor, which is one of the fiber-optic sensors, can measure internal states of specimens by embedding. This sensor was used in many studies on damage detection and monitoring of CFRTP manufacturing processes. We have investigated internal strain changes of relatively thin CFRTP laminates during molding process [6]. It was confirmed that residual compressive strain increased as the cooling speed decreased. However, there is no previous research that targeted internal strain changes of thick CFRTP laminates due to skin-core effects.

In this study, we first focus on the in-plane transverse behavior of uni-directional thick CF/PPS laminates. The embedded FBG sensor is applied to monitor the internal strain changes and evaluate the residual strain distribution due to skin-core effects during molding and annealing processes. Furthermore, we conduct tensile tests of cross-ply thick laminates to investigate the effects of residual stress distribution on the mechanical property.

2 SKIN-CORE EFFECTS

CFRTP products are often manufactured by hot-press molding. Before pressing process, a CFRTP laminate is rapidly heated by an infrared heater. When the laminate reaches the temperature higher than the melting temperature (T_m) of the thermoplastic resin, the laminate can be pressed and the shape can be changed from flat to the die configuration such as L-shape. The temperature of the die configuration (T_{dc}) is one of the most important parameters for molding of CFRTP products because this temperature condition determines the heat transfer behavior and the cooling speed. When T_{dc} is relatively lower than T_m , products can be cooled quickly and thus high-cycle manufacturing is possible. However, there is a possibility of degrading the product quality.

Selection of T_{dc} for thick laminates is more important than that of thin laminates because temperature distribution is generated during the cooling process in the through-thickness direction. When T_{dc} is set at room temperature, for example, the surface of thick laminates is cooled down and solidified in a moment. Meanwhile, the central part is still melting. Therefore, the non-uniform temperature causes the distribution of the start time of solidification (Fig. 1). First, the solidified surface part becomes rigid and disturbs solidification behavior in the central part. This results in a parabolic distribution of residual stress; the surface part has residual compressive stress and the central part has residual tensile stress. This behavior is often called as “thermal skin-core effects”.

Figure 1: The mechanism of thermal skin-core effects.

Not only temperature distribution but also cooling speed distribution is sometimes generated. Cooling speed distribution also causes the skin-core effect on crystallization. Crystalline thermoplastic resins shrink at the crystallization temperature (T_c) and they become structurally stable. Moreover, crystallinity generally depends on cooling speed; the faster the laminate is cooled, the lower the crystallinity becomes. Therefore, the amount of shrinkage due to crystallization distributes in the presence of cooling speed distribution. This behavior also causes residual stress/strain distribution in the through-thickness direction. This is called as “morphological skin-core effects”.

In this study, three cooling conditions were adapted to evaluate each skin-core effect. The characteristics of three conditions are summarized in Table 1. The first condition is “Natural Cooling (NC)”. The laminates of NC condition can be cooled uniformly without any distribution of temperature and cooling speed. Therefore, an influence of the skin-core effects is the smallest in these three conditions. The second condition is “Water Cooling (WC)”. This condition introduces only temperature distribution in laminates. It means that thermal skin-core effects can be evaluated by this one. The last condition is “Cold Press (CP)”. This condition has the fastest cooling speed and induces cooling speed distribution as well as temperature distribution. Therefore, laminates of CP show the mixture results of thermal and morphological skin-core effects. An influence of morphological effects can be evaluated by a comparison of WC and CP results.

Cooling Conditions	Temperature distribution	Cooling speed distribution	Type of Skin-Core effects
Natural Cooling (NC)	×	×	No Skin-Core
Water Cooling (WC)	○	×	Thermal
Cold Press (CP)	○	○	Thermal + Morphological

Table 1: The characteristics of three cooling conditions.

3 FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

FBG sensor is one of the optical fiber sensors. This sensor has significant advantages such as lightweight, immunity to magnetic interference, and high-sensitivity. Thus, an embedded FBG sensor can evaluate internal changes of the measuring object with a minimal invasive manner. Fig. 2 illustrates the schematic view of an FBG sensor. The principle of this sensor is Bragg reflection. Periodic change of refractive index which is processed into the core of optical fiber plays a role as the Bragg grating. As a result, narrow-band spectrum reflects from the grating as shown in Fig. 3. The center wavelength of reflected light, λ_B is written as:

$$\lambda_B = 2n_0\Lambda \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the grating length and n_0 is the initial refractive index. When the grating length changes due to strain or temperature, λ_B shifts according to the equation (1). The shift amount of wavelength $\Delta\lambda$ can be expressed by the linear sum of axial strain change $\Delta\varepsilon$ and temperature change ΔT . This relational expression is written as

$$\Delta\lambda = C_s \times \Delta\varepsilon + C_T \times \Delta T \quad (2)$$

where C_s and C_T are the sensitivity parameters. Preliminary calibration tests determined these parameters to be $C_s = 1.2$ [pm/ $\mu\varepsilon$] and $C_T = 12.26$ [pm/ $^\circ\text{C}$].

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of FBG sensor.

Figure 3: Reflected spectrum with narrow band.

3 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR UD THICK LAMINATES

The specimens were fabricated from uni-directional CF/PPS prepreg (AS4/TC1000, TenCate Co., Ltd.). PPS resin is one of the crystalline thermoplastics. Thermal properties of CF/PPS are provided in Table 2. The shape and size of the specimens are shown in Fig. 4. The stacking sequence was [0₄/FBG-90_s/0₂₀/FBG-90_c/0₂₄]. FBG-90_s denotes the sensor embedded perpendicularly to the carbon fibers direction between the 4 and 5 plies (i.e., surface part of laminates). FBG-90_c was embedded between the 24 and 25 plies (i.e., central part of laminates). The grating length of FBG sensors was 1mm. K-type thermocouples were also embedded in the same layer with FBG sensors. The specimens were lapped with polyimide films (UPILEX, thickness: 12.5 μm) to suppress the resin flow and the deformation after melting.

The specimens were molded between a pair of heating-cooling copper plates attached to a universal hydraulic tester for pressure control. The two copper plates can heat and cool the specimens by built-in cartridge heaters and cooling water. During the heating and isothermal process, temperature was controlled by the heaters within a range from 20°C to 330°C. During the cooling process, the specimens were cooled by three cooling conditions as shown in Table 1. Pressure was kept at 0.1MPa during molding in the NC and WC conditions. The specimen manufactured by the CP condition was pressed at 0.1MPa from the beginning of cooling.

All specimens were also annealed to increase the crystallinity and evaluate the effects of crystallinity on the residual strain distributions. During annealing, the specimens were heated and pressed in the same way as the molding process. The specimens must be annealed below the melting temperature (T_m) to avoid the melting of crystals and also must be heated slowly to promote recrystallization. Anneal temperature was set at 260°C and heating speed was 2°C/min. Cooling speed was about -10°C/min controlled by natural cooling. During annealing, the specimens were pressed under 0.01MPa to minimize the effects of pressure.

Glass-transition temperature (T_g)	Melting temperature (T_m)	Crystallization temperature (T_c)
93 °C	280 °C	235 °C

Table 2: The thermal properties of CF/PPS.

Figure 4: Schematic of specimen.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION (MOLDING PROCESS)

We targeted the internal strain changes induced by skin-core effects generated during the cooling process. It is necessary to determine the reference point to evaluate strain changes and residual strain. Thus, the state before cooling was defined as the reference point because temperature was almost same with each specimen.

4.1 Natural cooling condition

Figure 5a shows the temperature history of NC condition. The specimen was cooled uniformly and maximum temperature difference between the surface and the central part was only 5.5°C. Cooling speed was -8°C/min so that crystallinity became relatively high. Figure 5b shows the strain changes of the surface and central part. The compressive strain increased below 250°C due to the thermal and crystalline shrinkage. This temperature was near the T_c . Thus, the stiffness of PPS resin increased and contraction of the material was sensitively transferred to the FBG sensors. Residual strain was defined by the strain at the end of the molding. The residual compressive strain was about 20000 $\mu\epsilon$ and the strain difference between the surface and the central part was only 800 $\mu\epsilon$. It was confirmed that the NC laminates contracted almost uniformly and skin-core effects were negligible.

4.2 Water cooling condition

Figures 6a and 6b show the results of WC condition. There was no cooling speed distribution but temperature distribution existed. The maximum temperature difference was about 80°C and the cooling speed was about -170°C/min. Therefore, the thermal skin-core effect was generated. The strain change soon after the beginning of cooling differed from that of NC condition due to the thermal skin-core effect. The amount of compressive strain of the central part generated at stage I (Fig. 6b) was higher than that of NC condition. This is because the central part at the melting state was contracted by the thermal and crystalline shrinkage of the surface part that was solidified in advance. However, the compressive strain of the central part generated at stage II (Fig. 6b) was lower than that of NC condition. In contrast, though it was expected that the residual compressive strain of the surface part would be low due to the relatively low crystallinity caused by high speed cooling, residual strain was almost the same with that of NC condition. This is attributed to the residual stress due to the thermal skin-core effect (Fig. 1). The geometrical constraint from the surface part that shrank in advance suppressed the contraction of the central part. The residual strain difference between the surface and central parts was large (4880 $\mu\epsilon$). As a result, tensile (compressive) stress existed in the central (surface) part after molding. However, it is difficult to investigate the residual stress distribution of UD thick laminates experimentally. Therefore, the residual stress distribution due to skin-core effects was evaluated by tensile tests of cross-ply thick laminates that will be detailed later.

4.3 Cold press condition

Figures 7a and 7b show the results of CP condition. In this condition, not only temperature distribution but also cooling speed distribution was generated. The maximum temperature difference was about 170°C. The cooling speed of the surface part was -880°C/min and that of the central part was -150°C/min. This leads to a large crystallinity distribution. Therefore, thermal and morphological skin-core effects existed. Strain change of CP condition was again different between the surface and central parts as well as that of WC. The amount of compressive strain in each part was smaller than that of WC by 5000 $\mu\epsilon$. This is attributed to the low crystallinity caused by the extremely high cooling speed. Moreover, the difference of residual compressive strain between the surface and central parts was 5375 $\mu\epsilon$ which was larger than that of WC. It was successfully confirmed that skin-core effects can be monitored by embedded FBG sensors and distribution of residual strain is possible to be evaluated quantitatively.

Figure 5a: Temperature history of NC condition.

Figure 5b: Strain changes of NC condition.

Figure 6a: Temperature history of WC condition.

Figure 6b: Strain changes of WC condition.

Figure 7a: Temperature history of CP condition.

Figure 7b: Strain changes of CP condition.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION (ANNEALING PROCESS)

CFRTP is occasionally annealed to relax a portion of the residual stresses, to lower the residual stress gradients through the thickness of the laminates, or simply to obtain optimal levels of

crystallinity [1]. Moreover, the morphological skin-core effect for residual strain can be investigated by annealing. The manufactured specimens were annealed at 260°C and the strain changes were monitored by the embedded FBG sensors. Figure 8 presents the temperature history of the surface and central parts during the annealing process. This history was almost the same in each specimen due to the slow heating and cooling.

5.1 Natural cooling condition

Figure 9 shows the strain change of NC specimen during annealing. The strain of the start point was defined as 0 $\mu\epsilon$. This specimen had uniform and high crystallinity before annealing. Thus, the compressive strain in each part after annealing was the same; about 1500 $\mu\epsilon$.

5.2 Water cooling condition

Figure 10 presents the strain change of WC specimen during annealing. This specimen had uniform and relatively low crystallinity before annealing. The strain change in each part was almost the same as in NC specimen. However, the strain change in each part after annealing was higher than that of NC specimen. Since the difference of compressive strain did not disappear after annealing, the residual strain due to the thermal skin-core effect was not relaxed or canceled.

5.3 Cold press condition

Figure 11 shows the results of CP specimen during annealing. The strain change differed between the surface and central parts due to the non-uniform crystallinity distribution. The strain curve of the surface part deviated from that of the central part above 100°C because recrystallization occurred above T_g . As a result, the compressive strain of the surface part was higher than that of the central part by about 800 $\mu\epsilon$ after annealing. This is because crystalline shrinkage of the surface part, which had the extremely low crystallinity, was larger than that of the central part.

The cooling speed of the central part in CP specimen in the time of manufacturing was roughly the same with that in WC specimen. Therefore, it was expected that almost the same compressive strain would be generated due to annealing in the both specimens. However, the amount of generated compressive strain in the case of CP was higher than that of WC. This is because the shrinkage of the central part in CP specimen due to recrystallization was affected by the surface part with the extremely low crystallinity. Thus, it was confirmed that the residual compressive (tensile) stress was generated in the central (surface) part by annealing. It was an opposite behavior to the thermal skin-core effect. Therefore, annealing has a potential to reduce the residual stress distribution induced by skin-core effects in the case of CP specimens.

Figure 8: Temperature history during annealing.

Figure 9: Strain changes of NC specimen.

Figure 10: Strain changes of WC specimen.

Figure 11: Strain changes of CP specimen.

6 RESIDUAL STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN CROSS-PLY THICK LAMINATES

Then, we evaluated the effects of residual stress distribution in thick CFRTP laminates on the mechanical property. The specimens for this test were cross-ply laminates. The stacking sequence was $[0/90_4]_9/0$. The molding method was the same as the UD laminates. However, the specimens were cooled by only NC and CP conditions and pressed at 1.25MPa to decrease voids, which could affect the mechanical property. After manufacturing, laminates were cut into specimens with 90mm length and 15mm width. The cross-section of each specimen was polished with sandpapers. The number of transverse cracks which occurred in each 90-degree layer was counted after applying 0, 1000, 2000, 3000, 4000, and 5000 $\mu\epsilon$. The strain was measured by a strain gage that was pasted on the surface of specimens. The test was conducted twice in each cooling condition.

6.1 Results and discussion

Figures 12a, 12b, 12c, and 12d show the transverse cracks density in each 90-degree layer at 0, 1000, 3000, and 5000 $\mu\epsilon$. NC specimens have micro cracks in all the 90-degree layers before tensile testing. In contrast, there were no cracks in CP specimens. This is because thermal and crystalline shrinkage of the 90-degree layer was constrained by the 0-degree layer, which resulted in residual tensile stress. Especially in NC specimens, the resin had high crystallinity so that the residual tensile stress was higher than CP specimens. Cracks in CP specimens occurred after the strain reached 2000 $\mu\epsilon$. The crack density of the central part (sections: 4,5,6) was higher than that of the surface part (sections : 1,2,8,9). The residual tensile stress of the central part induced the premature cracks. In contrast, the crack density of NC specimens was almost uniform in the through-thickness direction.

The crack density of the central part in all specimens after 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ reached about 10/cm, however, that of the surface part in CP specimens was still lower than 10/cm. As a result, it was confirmed that the skin-core effects have a potential to distribute the residual stress in laminates and cause the premature fracture.

Residual strain of UD specimens can be evaluated by the embedded FBG sensors as shown in Figures. 5b, 6b, and 7b. If it is assumed that the residual strain of cross-ply specimens, which would be small, can be measured, then the residual stress generated in the 90-degree layers can be estimated by the comparison of residual strain between UD and cross-ply specimens generally. Moreover, it is suggested that we can consider the residual stress due to skin-core effects in detail with a combination of the results of tensile tests and monitoring of molding processes. However, the precise evaluation of residual stress development and distribution due to the skin-core effects should be done by the numerical analysis with some visco-elastic and crystallization models. This detail analysis and measurement would be a help to improve the molding conditions that can suppress the distributions of the product qualities.

Figure 12a: The transverse crack density of specimens in each layer at $0\mu\epsilon$.

Figure 12b: The transverse crack density of specimens in each layer at $1000\mu\epsilon$.

Figure 12c: The transverse crack density of specimens in each layer at $3000\mu\epsilon$.

Figure 12d: The transverse crack density of specimens in each layer at $5000\mu\epsilon$.

7 CONCLUSIONS

It was reported that the skin-core effects have a potential to make the distributions of residual stress/strain and material property. These distributions were the specific problem for a thick CFRTP laminate because the start time of solidifying was different in the through-thickness direction due to temperature distribution and cooling speed distribution. In-situ monitoring of the strain change during the molding process due to these effects has never been evaluated. Thus, we investigated the in-plane transverse strain change and residual strain development of UD thick CF/PPS laminates during the three different cooling methods; NC, WC, and CP using two FBG sensors. They were embedded into the surface and central locations of specimens. As a result, it was confirmed that the strain change in the surface part was different from that of the central one in the case of WC and CP specimens with non-uniform temperature distribution. This is because the surface part which solidified in advance disturbed the solidification of the central part. Therefore, residual compressive strain of the surface part was higher than that of the central one at least $4880\mu\epsilon$. Moreover, residual compressive (tensile) stress existed in the surface (central) part of specimens. In contrast, NC specimens with an uniform temperature distribution had almost the same residual strain. Moreover, all specimens were annealed at high temperature to evaluate the effect of crystallinity distribution due to the difference of cooling

speed on residual strain. Since CP specimens had not only temperature distribution but also crystallinity distribution, the amount of compressive strain due to annealing differed from part to part. Thus, it was confirmed that the amount of crystalline shrinkage in the surface part was larger than the central part. The residual stress distribution was then investigated by tensile tests of thick cross-ply specimens which were manufactured by NC and CP conditions. In the tests, we counted transverse cracks in the nine sections with the 90-degree fiber direction. NC specimens before tensile testing had many micro cracks because of high thermal stress and large crystalline shrinkage. In the case of CP specimens, the crack density of the central part was higher than that of the surface part after applying 3000 $\mu\epsilon$ due to skin-core effects. It was evident that residual tensile (compressive) stress existed in the central (surface) part of CP specimens. In contrast, the crack density of NC specimens was almost uniform in the through-thickness direction during tensile testing. This study demonstrated that the residual strain distribution due to skin-core effects can be evaluated by embedded FBG sensors and skin-core effects significantly affected the mechanical property of thick CFRTP laminates. We will investigate the mechanism of residual stress/strain development due to skin-core effects by finite element analysis in detail and propose an optimal molding condition that can suppress the distributions of the product qualities.

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